

6.2.2.4. Initiative Assessment

To assess how policy instruments have affected initiatives on the ground, we first compiled a list of global and large regional initiatives, and then assessed case studies within these initiatives.

6.2.2.4.1 Methodological approach to assess existing global and international initiatives against diverse value approaches

To more deeply investigate consequences of narrow and plural value approaches in and for policy, we assessed 46 initiatives that are active at global or large regional scales. We define initiatives as an agency, movement or organisation that works at a large regional or global scale and manages or influences (e.g. funds) multiple projects on the ground. For inclusion in our list of initiatives, we had to ascertain that an agency, organization or movement:

- Oversees or (aims to) influence place-based projects, programmes, policy and decisions related to conservation of biodiversity and ecosystem services;
- Is active over large regional (e.g. continental/subcontinental) or global scales;
- Concern outcomes that link to biodiversity and ecosystem services;
- advocate knowledge and awareness regarding narrow, plural, or both values within its project activities;
- Has project and institutional documents available in the project domain

To identify initiatives, we used the following search criteria using Google Search, and screened them against the inclusion criteria: “*Environmental project*”, “*Ecosystem service valuation initiative*”, “*Ecosystem service valuation project*”, “*Biodiversity project*”, “*Biodiversity initiative*”, “*Nature Project*”, “*Environmental Project*”. We also used “*Environmental valuation initiative*”, and “*Environmental valuation capacity building*”.

We also reviewed a database of policy support tools (IPBES Global Assessment) to include any support tools that qualified under our initiative definition

Upon establishment of our initiative list, we conducted a superficial assessment on the inclusion of diverse value approaches in each initiative, based on the initiatives’ mission, vision, and “about”, and “project web pages.

We assessed each initiative against the following criteria.

- *Value(s) being addressed (based on IPBES typology: holistic value, health value, economic value, socio-cultural value, biophysical value) explicitly addressed in the description of the initiative, its mission and vision, and description of projects/work*
- *Values typology (intrinsic, instrumental, relational)*

- *Diverse values present or not. We considered an initiative to have diverse value inclusion when more than one value type (relational, instrumental, and intrinsic) was addressed in the*
- *Whether or not the vision, mission and “about us” pages considered indigenous and local knowledge*
- *The IPBES region where an initiative was active (i.e. Africa, America, Europe-Central Asia, Asia-Pacific, Global)*
- *Dominant Decision Making context: Use, Conservation or Development*
- *Does it include Targeted Policy Themes?*
- *Does it speak to Grand Challenges?*
- *Goals/Objectives of Initiative*
- *Work area boundary (Glob, Reg, Nat, Sub-nat, Ecosystm, Sect)*
- *Decision makers targeted*

Characteristic	Coding	Coding explanation
Plural Values being addressed	Hc	Holistic value
	Heal	Health value
<i>Based on IPBES' plural values typology</i>	Econ	Economic value
	SoC	Socio-cultural value
	Biop	Biophysical value
Types of Values evident	Int	Intrinsic
	Ins	Instrumental value
	Rel	Relational value
Plural values explicitly addressed in the	Yes	Implicitly or explicitly addressed In the mission, vision or value statement of an initiative

mission, vision, value statement of initiatives	No	Not implicitly or explicitly addressed in the mission, vision or value statement of an initiative
ILK addressed	Yes/No	Is ILK mentioned in the mission/vision/value statement or descriptions of type of projects supported
Region/Scale	Glob	Global
	AP	Asia Pacific
<i>Based on IPBES' Regions</i>	Af	Africa
	EuCA	Europe and Central Asia
	Amrc	America
Dominant decision-making contexts	Conservation	Incl. protection and restoration, with the aim of supporting positive effects on nature
<i>Based on Ch4 typology on the decision-making contexts</i>	Development	understood in the traditional sense (mining, infrastructure, agricultural expansion, urbanization etc.) where the aim would be to avoid harm on nature
	Use	refers to access or management of nature, might include sharing/reallocation of benefits and rights -- consultation and involvement of the local stakeholders on resources use
Pet policies	BD	TBD post-CBD (0-2 coding)
	CGA	Corporate Green Accounting (0-2 coding)

	Edu	education (0-2 coding)
Hot Potatoes	Trans	rapid, large-scale transformations (e.g. large infrastructure, large plantation agriculture, rapid urbanization)
	AgF	agriculture and food (extensification vs intensification, agro-ecological vs monoculture approaches, farmers, corporation vs IPLCs)
	Fish	fisheries (small scale vs industrial, coastal vs oceans)
	PA	Protected areas for biodiversity as policy implementation measure for conservation management (and associated win/lose conflicts)
Goals/Objectives	Mainst	Awareness raising, mainstreaming
<i>As advised in the projects' brief/webpage</i>	CapStg	Capacity strengthening, knowledge improvement
	PolAdvoc	Inform, influence, or advocate policy, <i>including trade-off</i>
	StkEng	Stakeholder engagement
Work area boundary	Glob	Global
<i>Based on the summary of the current findings</i>	Reg	Regional, <i>based on IPBES regions</i>

	Nat	National
	Sub-nat	Sub-national <i>i.e. province, state, municipal, district, etc</i>
	Ecosyst	Ecosystem <i>i.e. marine, mangrove, forest, urban, etc</i>
	Sect	Sectors <i>i.e. water, energy, climate, etc</i>
Target stakeholders	Comm	Local community
	NGO	NGO
	S-NatG	Sub-national government
	NatG	National government
	Yout	Youth & Children
	Bus	Private/business sectors
	SciAcad	University and academia
	Don	Donor/International organisation
Decision makers targeted	Int	Intergovernmental Organizations
Based on IPBES decision maker typology, Global assessment chapter 6	Grn	Governments (national, subnational, local)

	NGO	NGOs
	Comm	Citizens, community groups, farmers
	IPLC	IPLC
	Donor	Donor agencies
	Sci	Science and educational organizations
	Corp	Corporate Actors

Initiatives Protocol

The “superficial” assessment of initiatives allowed us to assess how initiatives were generally aspiring to diverse value approaches, but to assess how diverse value approaches in policy were used to facilitate transformative governance, we assessed specific case studies that documented evidence of policy support for transformative governance.

To identify case study for each initiative, we used one of two approaches:

1. We searched the SCOPUS and Web of Science databases using the following search string: “[name of initiative]” AND “values” AND “policy” AND “transformative governance” OR “status quo” OR “institutional change” OR “capacity building” OR “integration” OR “adaptation”
2. Where an above search yielded no results, or papers that did not provide sufficient information or evidence, we also used case studies reported on the initiative’s web page.

We balanced case studies by region, and specifically selected case studies that involved IPLCs. Generally, we selected case studies that presented more evidence on how policies could support transformative governance.

We assessed each of the example initiatives in the same way as we assessed the bright spot cases.